

Moderating Discussions on Miro

Discussion sessions will not be recorded.

Discussion Breakouts on Day 2

Logistics slides with room and topic assignments: <https://tinyurl.com/Day2Disc>
https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1vq9Q_wFZ9JB7Qlz3a18KVBnoz2XtDnA_u7E4npFp3k/w/edit?usp=sharing

- **Before the session begins**, copy the discussion topic and description into BOTH the Miro board and the google document.
- Ask who in the room is the notetaker. If no one responds, as for a volunteer.
- First, guide them from the agenda to the correct google doc for the session. If in-person, direct them to the workshop poster for the QR code. Place this link in the Webex chat.

Wednesday, May 8, 2024		
Time (ET)	Agenda Item	Presenter/Notes
Day 2: Community Software Efforts at NASA - Opportunities and Challenges		Day 2 Google Folder Morning Moderator: Demitri Muna Afternoon Moderator: Brian Thomas
9:30 am - 9:50 am	Invited Talk on Community Software Efforts at NASA	Julie Barnum
9:50 am - 10:30 am	Software at NASA: Highlighted Talks with Q&A	Ross Beyer Luis Lopez David Aronchick Ziheng Sun
10:30 am - 10:35 am	Logistics of Breakouts	Rebecca Ringuette
10:35 am - 11:20 am	Software at NASA: Lightning Breakout 1	(See Lightning Folder)
11:20 am - 11:35 am	<i>Break (15 minutes)</i>	
11:35 am - 12:20 pm	Software at NASA: Lightning Breakout 2	

- Begin by having all attendees sign in to the google notes doc.
- Introductions are fine IF less than 3 minutes total, but avoid spending a lot of time on this.
- Direct people to the miro board. Show the miro board at the front of the room. Demo and describe how to navigate around the miro board. Make sure to state the **rules**:
 - **Do not edit, delete, or cover up another person's note.**
 - **Add comments by adding a note next to the one you are commenting on.**
 - **Verbal and written should be concise to allow others to speak and other notes to be seen.**
- Frame the discussion to focus on opportunities and challenges for the discussion topic. If you are comfortable, give an idea or two of your own to get them thinking. Ask the attendees to contribute a few initial thoughts on the topic.
- After ~5 minutes, direct the attendees to write down a few opportunities and challenges they can think of that are directly related to the discussion topic. Give at least 5 minutes of silence for this, up to 10 minutes.
- When the rate of entries slows down, start the discussion again by asking the attendees to comment on a note you think might be a good direction for the discussion. Repeat as needed. Encourage them to keep adding notes to the board as relevant.
- Keep the discussion focused on challenges and opportunities without diving too deep into the details.
- During the last 10 minutes, redirect the attendees to the google notes doc to work towards agreement on the 3-5 most important takeaways and priorities from the discussion to share with the rest of the workshop attendees. You may also choose to have this discussion on the bottom portion of the miro board.
- **Make sure to end on time.**

Paths Forward Breakouts on Day 3

Logistics slides with room and topic assignments: <https://tinyurl.com/Day3Paths>
https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1gpAEJqeivr_yZ1mA7b298dejacwIL83KwlnMttwSP2Y/e_dit?usp=sharing

- **Before the session begins**, copy the discussion topic and description from the logistics breakout slides into the google notes document for your session. **If you would like to have a miro board for this portion, please email me to request one.** (rebecca.ringuette@nasa.gov)
- Ask who in the room is the notetaker. If no one responds, ask for a volunteer.
- **NOTE: These sessions may become hybrid.** If that happens, please check the WebEx interface often for comments or raised hands for the virtual attendees, and place the link for the session's google doc in the chat.
- Direct attendees in your session to the google notes doc associated with the session. Ask all attendees to sign in on the notes doc.
- Guide the discussion for attendees to provide potential paths forward, solutions, and other input for the assigned priority. Give 3-5 minutes to discuss possible paths forward.
- Give 5-10 minutes of silence for attendees to add suggestions on how progress could be made for each, such as potential actions, workshops, outlining what is missing and so on.
- Discuss a few of the paths forward with the remaining time. Encourage attendees to continue to add paths forward.
- In some cases, this may evolve into outlining a proposal for a workshop, software development needed, or other related effort. That is okay!
- During the last 10 minutes, prepare a few takeaways or a summary of progress for the immediately following report back session.
- **Make sure to end on time.**